

Comparison of Gain Increase in Spoof Surface Plasmon Polaritons Antennas with PEC and AMC Grounds

Mahdi Siasifar^{1,*}, Asghar Keshtkar², Shervin Amiri

^{1&2} Faculty of Technical and Engineering, Imam Khomeini International University, Qazvin, Iran

² Electrical and Information Technology Department, Iranian Research Organization for Science and Technology (IROST), Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

Recent studies propose replacing perfect electric conductor (PEC) grounds with artificial magnetic conductor (AMC) grounds to achieve a lower profile and better performance. This paper studies and compares the increase in radiation gain and performance of a wideband spoof surface plasmon polaritons (SSPP) Ku-band satellite reception leaky wave planar antenna (LWPA), with four different PEC and AMC ground structures. All ground structures are simulated, optimized and compared by CST Studio software over the wide Ku frequency band of 10.7 GHz to 12.75 GHz. Unlike earlier narrowband, low-frequency studies that showed equal gain for PEC and AMC grounds (with AMC providing a lower profile), our study demonstrates that the PEC ground offers twice the increased gain bandwidth (2.05 GHz vs. 1.05 GHz) and the trade-off for a lower profile with an AMC ground is steep, requiring a 50% bandwidth reduction for just a 16.74% size decrease. Therefore, PEC ground is a better choice for the studied antenna and frequency band. SSPP KU-band LWPAs are finding wide applications in 5G, 6G, geostationary (GSO) and none-geostationary (NGSO) satellite communications and optimized selection of the ground type can have a great impact on the overall final characteristics of the antenna.

Keywords: Artificial magnetic conductor (AMC); perfect electric conductor (PEC); perfect magnetic conductor (PMC); spoof surface plasmon polaritons (SSPP) antenna; Wideband planar satellite reception antennas;

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the simplest ways to increase the gain of an antenna, is making it more directional by placing a reflector in a specific distance in one side of the antenna to reflect back the transmitted or received waves in such a way that the combined effect of the direct and reflected waves at far field, results in a wave with higher magnitude. This can only happen if the two waves are in phase, i.e., the difference between the phase of the two waves, equals to an integer multiple of 2π [1]. Traditionally, the reflector is made by a simple metal sheet that can theoretically be modeled as a perfect electric conductor (PEC) that reflects the wave with same amplitude, but inverted phase. The total phase difference of the reflected wave and the original wave in an arbitrary point, is the sum of the constant 180° inversion caused by reflection from a PEC and the phase difference caused by the extra route that reflected wave travels with respect to direct wave. This phase difference is a function of the frequency of the propagated wave and the optimized PEC distance from the antenna [1]. The dependency of the optimized distance of PEC ground from the antenna on frequency, can increase the overall antenna profile in some frequencies. One way to decrease this distance is to eliminate the 180° phase inversion of the PEC reflector by using a perfect magnetic conductor (PMC) [1] that by definition reflects the wave with the same amplitude and phase as the incident wave. Unlike PEC, PMC is not naturally found in nature, but it is possible to use structures that act similar to PMC in a certain frequency range. These artificially made structures are called artificial magnetic conductors or AMCs. Obviously, the amplitude and the phase of reflection coefficient (Γ) of AMC, is a function of frequency, and the simultaneous phase and

amplitude conditions of the PMC can only occur at a single frequency. But it is possible to find a frequency range in which the amplitude and phase conditions are approximately met simultaneously. Usually, a reflecting surface is considered to act as AMC in a frequency range in which the amplitude of Γ approximately equals to one and the absolute value of phase of Γ is less than 90° [2,3]. This range is usually calculated for normal incident waves and can decrease if the incident angle is declined. The dependency of AMC ground behavior to incident angle is a weakness in comparison to PEC grounds that behave the same for all incident angles. Theoretically, as the amplitude of Γ in AMC is also near to one, in a same way as PEC, it can increase the gain by a maximum of 3dB. In addition to increasing the gain, AMC ground may also lead to a smaller antenna profile with respect to PEC ground in certain frequencies due to the zero-phase shift in reflection [4-6]. As most of the surfaces that support AMC property have discontinuity in their metallic sections, they can have large surface impedance in certain frequency ranges. Therefore, if the design parameters of AMC are carefully tailored, the high surface impedance frequency range can overlap the AMC frequency range [7] and suppress the unwanted surface waves created in PEC antenna grounds. Hence, AMC ground can also decrease some undesired phenomena such as gratings and back lobes. In summary, AMC grounds can decrease the antenna profile and also eliminate unwanted surface waves and therefore many efforts have been made to replace PEC grounds by AMC grounds in different antenna structures [8-10].

The implementation of planar antennas in wireless and satellite communications is growing widely due to their numerous benefits [11]. Different types of planar antennas have been introduced. We have discussed the development of a growing category of leaky-wave planar antennas (LWPAs) called designer or spoof surface plasmon polaritons (SSPP) antenna in our earlier work [12] in which we designed an optimized rectangular patch SSPP antenna for high gain multi branch antenna arrays used in 10.7 GHz to 12.75 GHz Ku satellite reception band which is widely used by conventional Geostationary satellite communication and emerging non-geostationary satellite constellations. [4] studied and compared the effect of PEC and PMC (AMC) ground in propagation gain and total profile of a narrow band SSPP antenna in the frequency range of 4.5-6.5 GHz and showed that although both PEC and AMC can both increase the propagating gain of SSPP antenna up to 3 dB, but using AMC ground leads to antenna profile reduction of about 53%. As was mentioned earlier, the ground distance in both PEC and AMC is a function of frequency and in higher frequencies, the change in antenna profile can lead to completely different results and should be studied separately. For example, the PMC used in [4] at 4.5-6.5 GHz frequency range; that is approximately half the frequency we study here; is a periodic metallic square patch over a dielectric layer and a ground plane located only 2 mm under AMC.

In this letter we study the effect of PEC and AMC ground on propagation gain of SSPP antennas in Ku band satellite reception band for a SSPP antenna we developed in our earlier work [12]. We first place a PEC ground under the designed SSPP antenna and then simulate and optimize the distance of the ground plane by maximizing the gain of the antenna using results template of post processing section of the Frequency solver of CST STUDIO commercial software. The antenna input is simulated by a waveguide port covering 0.75 of the central section of the width of the antenna in x direction and a height of $5*(t_d+t_m)$ in both z directions (See Fig. 1(c) for t_d and t_m definition). The default boundary conditions of the Frequency solver are used for these simulations. Then we repeat the simulation and optimization process for three different AMC ground structures with same software setting. The results are then discussed and compared. This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the AMC and SSPP antenna design. Section 3 discusses and compares the simulation results for a SSPP antenna with different antenna grounds including a PEC ground and three types of AMC grounds developed in section 2. Section 4 is the conclusion of this work.

2. AMC AND SSPP ANTENNA DESIGN

2.1. AMC Structure Selection

Early AMC structures use Electronic Band Gap (EBG) property of periodic metallic patches connected by vias to a ground located under the patches [8,13]. The fabrication of these structures is not easy due to the presence of a large number of vias. An alternative and efficient AMC type that is fabricated without any via, is periodic metallic patch structures that are placed on a dielectric plane [14-16]. As almost any new patch geometry leads to a new type of periodic metallic AMC surface, many different types of AMC surfaces are introduced [17-19]. [20] has studied some of the common metal patch types used in periodic AMC surfaces and concluded that simple periodic metallic square patches over a dielectric layer have better performance in comparison to the other studied types. Another criterion for AMC structure selection for any antenna is its

sensitivity to polarization. As we need a simple, easy to fabricate and insensitive to polarization AMC structure, we selected the periodic metallic square patch structure over a dielectric with a PEC ground under the dielectric. The PEC ground is either attached to the dielectric or separated with a space h from it. Figure 1 shows the periodic metallic square patch unit cell and 3D view of this structure. P is the period of patches, $P-P_g$ is the square patch width, h is the distance between dielectric and PEC ground and t_m and t_d are the metal and dielectric thicknesses, respectively. To model and simulate the periodic AMC structure and coupling effect of adjacent unit cells of the Fig. 1, we used CST STUDIO software with unit cell boundary condition across the xy surface that incorporates the Floquet ports in the direction normal to surface containing patches (z). We use Rogers RO4003C[®] substrate with dielectric relative permittivity (ϵ_r), loss tangent and thickness (t_d) of 3.55, 0.0027 and 0.813 mm, respectively. The dielectric is coated by copper with 35 μm thickness (t_m) (see Fig. 1(c)). The patch period ($p=5$ mm) and patch distance ($P_g=0.4$ mm) in Fig.1 are selected by wide band optimization of magnitude and phase conditions of the reflection coefficient (Γ) of AMC ground for $h=0$ mm that is shown in Fig. 2. These parameters are recalculated for each value of h . We use two other values of $h=1$ and 2 mm in our study. Higher values of h produce antenna profiles larger than those with PEC grounds and are therefore not used. Fig. 3 shows the simulated amplitude and phase of the reflection coefficient Γ for $h=1$ mm, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=1.1$ mm case and $h=2$ mm, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=1.7$ mm case. Comparison of Fig.2 and Fig. 3 shows that increasing h improves both magnitude and phase condition of AMC reflection.

Fig. 1. AMC built by Periodic metallic square patch (a) 3D view of unit cell with $p=5$ mm, $t_d=0.813$ mm, $t_m=35$ μm and $h=0, 1$ and 2 mm (b) top view of unit cell with period p and $P_g=0.4$ mm (c) side view of unit cell, (d) periodic metallic square patches over a Rogers RO4003C[®] substrate ($\epsilon_r=3.55$, loss tangent of 0.0027)

Fig. 2. (a) magnitude and (b) phase of reflection coefficient (Γ) of AMC ground of Fig. 1 when $h=0$ mm, $p=5$ mm and $P_g=0.4$ mm

Fig. 3. (a) magnitude and (b) phase of reflection coefficient (Γ) of AMC ground of Fig. 1 when $h=1$ mm, $p=5$ mm $P_g=1.1$ mm and $h=2$ mm, $p=5$ mm $P_g=1.7$ mm.

2.2. SSPP Antenna Structure

To study and compare the effect of adding PEC or AMC ground to a SSPP antenna, we use the rectangular patch SSPP antenna that we designed in our earlier work [12]. The antenna structure together with the details of SSPP transmission line (TL) used to feed its patches and dimensions of its elements is shown in Fig. 4. The simulated gain of the antenna without any ground is shown in Fig. 5.

2.3. Simulation Results for SSPP Antenna Structure with PEC and AMC Grounds

In order to study the effect of adding different ground types to a groundless antenna structure, first we add a PEC ground with distance D_g under the antenna of Fig. 4. The SSPP antenna with PEC ground is shown in Fig. 6. The simulation shows that the antenna gain is optimized at $D_g=6$ mm. The optimized simulated gain of SSPP antenna with PEC ground is shown in Fig. 7. Comparison of Fig. 7 and Fig. 5 shows an approximate 3dB increase of the antenna gain for most of the simulated bandwidth, except for the 11.15 GHz that an unwanted resonance occurs in the antenna. This resonance is created due to antenna dimensions and can be eliminated or mitigated by changing antenna dimensions or capacitive or inductive loading. Also, the antenna gain with PEC ground is higher than antenna gain without ground at all simulated frequency band, even at the unwanted resonance frequency.

Fig. 4. SSPP antenna with rectangular patch (a) details of SSPP-TL used to feed rectangular patches with 50Ω CPW input/output interfaces, $d=5$ mm, $g=0.4$ mm, $r=2.3$ mm, total length of $L=22*d$ and $W=35$ mm, flaring ground with ellipse starting at $2.5*d$, minor axis radius of $2.5*d$, and major axis radius of $((W-d)/2)-g$ (b) top view of SSPP antenna with no ground and total length of $L=260$ mm, (c) an enlarged section of top view of SSPP antenna, $\lambda_{g1}=20.8$ mm $\lambda_{g2}=17.6$ mm, $L_p=\lambda_{g2}/4=4.4$ mm, $W=37$ mm, $D_p=13.52$ mm, $W_p=2.6$ mm [12].

Fig. 5. Simulated gain of the SSPP antenna without any ground

Fig. 6. SSPP antenna of Fig.3 with PEC ground [12]

Fig. 7. Optimized gain of SSPP antenna with PEC ground at $D_g=6$ mm

Fig. 8 shows the general structure of groundless SSPP antenna of Fig. 3 with the AMC ground. First, we consider $h=0$ mm and simulate the antenna gain to find the optimized value of D_g . Figure 9 shows the antenna gain for $h=0$ mm, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=0.4$ mm and various D_g values. Unlike the PEC ground, the optimization process is not straight forward for AMC and a single value of D_g can't be easily found for all frequencies. Therefore, we considered $D_g=7$ mm as the relative optimum choice for ground distance when $h=0$ mm. For getting better results, we also try the $h=1$ and 2 mm. Fig. 10 shows antenna gain for $h=1$ mm, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=1.1$ mm and various D_g values. We considered $D_g=3$ mm as the relative optimum choice for ground distance when $h=1$ mm. Fig. 11 shows antenna gain for $h=2$ mm, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=1.7$ mm and various D_g values. We considered $D_g=2$ mm as the relative optimum choice for ground distance when $h=2$ mm. The overall antenna profile equals to $D_g+2 t_m + t_d$ for PEC ground (less than 7 mm) and $D_g+3 t_m + 2 t_d +h$ for AMC ground, therefore we analyzed the D_g values that corresponded to antenna profile of less than and equal to 7 mm. Larger antenna profiles is not studied as they have no preference with respect to optimized antenna profile with PEC ground.

Fig. 8. General structure of SSPP antenna of Fig. 3 with the AMC ground of Fig. 1

Fig. 9. Gain of antenna of Fig. 8 for $h=0$, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=0.4$ mm for different values of D_g

Fig. 10. Gain of antenna of Fig. 8 for $h=1$, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=1.1$ mm for different values of D_g

Fig. 11. Gain of antenna of Fig. 8 for $h=2$ mm, $p=5$ mm, $P_g=1.7$ mm for different values of D_g

3. Comparison of Results

Table 1 shows the main parameters of the studied SSPP antennas. The antenna gains for groundless antenna and optimized PEC ground and the three relatively optimized AMC grounds are depicted in Fig. 12 for comparison. Table I shows that PEC ground has the highest peak gain and widest bandwidth with gain improvement among the four studied antennas. It also shows that the 1.152 mm (16.74%) reduction in antenna profile achieved with the AMC ground comes at the non-reasonable cost of a 50% reduction in bandwidth and a 2 dB decrease in peak gain. The antenna with PEC ground has a reasonably low profile that creates no practical limitation in antenna manufacturing. Figure 12 shows that the SSPP antenna with PEC ground has higher gain with respect to groundless antenna in the whole studied frequency band of 10.7 GHz to 12.75 GHz that is used for satellite reception in Ku band. This figure demonstrates that in the studied frequency band, when using an AMC ground plane rather than a PEC ground, the gain exceeds that of the groundless antenna only in a portion of the bandwidth. The study of adding a PEC ground and 3 different AMC grounds to SSPP antenna shows different results with respect to other studies done by [4-6] in lower frequencies and narrow bandwidths.

Table 1. Summary of Main Parameters of Studied SSPP Antennas

Ground Type	Peak Gain dBi	D_g (mm)	Ant Profile (mm)	BW with Gain Improvement
PEC	19.25	6	6.883	2.05 GHz
AMC $h=0$	15	7	8.731	0.4 GHz
AMC $h=1$	17.2	3	5.731	1.05 GHz
AMC $h=2$	17	2	5.731	1.02 GHz

Fig. 12. The antenna gains for groundless antenna and optimized PEC ground and three relatively optimized AMC grounds

4. Conclusion

Previous research at lower frequencies [4] found that AMC grounds could increase gain as consistently as PEC grounds over a wide band, while allowing for a lower antenna profile. However, this study demonstrates that this effect is not universal and the performance of AMC grounds for SSPP antennas depends heavily on the specific operating frequency and bandwidth. We concluded that PEC ground can result in better gain for wideband leaky wave SSPP rectangular patch antennas in 10.7 GHz to 12.75 GHz Ku satellite reception band. One reason for this behavior can be the fact that AMC grounds are sensitive to angle of incident wave, and when frequency increases and distance of ground to the antenna decreases, the probability of oblique incident waves increases and degrades the efficiency of the AMC grounds with respect to PEC grounds that are not sensitive to oblique waves. This result is used to design high gain multibranch SSPP LWPA for satellite Ku band reception in our future works.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. P. Feresidis, G. Goussetis, S. Wang, and J. C. Vardaxoglou, "Artificial magnetic conductor surfaces and their application to low-profile high-gain planar antennas," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 53, no. 11, pp. 209–215, 2005, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2004.840528.
- [2] W. Yang, H. Wang, W. Che, and J. Wang, "A wideband and high-gain edge-fed patch antenna and array using artificial magnetic conductor structures," *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.*, vol. 12, pp. 769–772, 2013, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2013.2270943.
- [3] D. F. Sievenpiper, L. Zhang, R. Broas, and E. Yablonovitch, "High-impedance electromagnetic surfaces with forbidden bands at radio and microwave frequencies," *Terahertz and Gigahertz Photonics*, vol. 3795, no. 11, p. 154, 1999, doi: 10.1117/12.370159.
- [4] Q. Zhang, Q. Le Zhang, and Y. Chen, "Spoof Surface Plasmon Polariton Leaky-Wave Antennas Using Periodically Loaded Patches above PEC and AMC Ground Planes," *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.*, vol. 16, pp. 3014–3017, 2017, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2017.2758368.
- [5] Y. Li, Y. Bai, and J. Shen, "Study on radiation characteristics and parameter optimization of SSPP circularly polarized antenna based on finite element method analysis," *Int. J. Hous. Sci. Its Appl.*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 1214–1227, 2025, doi: 10.70517/ijhsa46394.
- [6] N. Bahari et al., "Antenna Performance Enhancement using AMC Structure for 5G Frequency Range," *J. Adv. Res. Appl. Sci. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 97–104, 2023, doi: 10.37934/araset.29.3.97104.
- [7] G. Goussetis, A. P. Feresidis, and J. C. Vardaxoglou, "Tailoring the AMC and EBG characteristics of periodic metallic arrays printed on grounded dielectric substrate," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 82–89, 2006, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2005.861575.
- [8] A. Foroozesh and L. Shafai, "Application of combined electric- and magnetic-conductor ground planes for antenna performance enhancement," *IEEE Can. J. Electr. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 33, no. 2, pp. 1–4, 2008, doi: 10.1109/CJECE.2008.4621833.
- [9] A. Verma, R. K. Arya, and S. N. Raghava, "Monopole Cavity Resonator Antenna with AMC and Superstrate for 5G/WiMAX Applications," *Def. Sci. J.*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 51–60, 2023, doi: 10.14429/DSJ.73.17759.

- [10] A. M. Sonagara and R. Singh Kshetrimayum, "Broadside Radiation based on Even-mode Spoof Surface Plasmon Polaritons Excited by Slot in AMC Ground Plane," in 2022 3rd URSI Atlantic and Asia Pacific Radio Science Meeting (AT-AP-RASC), 2022, pp. 1–3. doi: 10.23919/AT-AP-RASC54737.2022.9814206.
- [11] P. Bahl, I. J., Bhartia, *Microstrip Antennas*. Artech House, 1980.
- [12] M. Siasifar, A. Keshkar, and S. Amiri, "Optimum Patch Selection for Wideband Planar Spoof Surface Plasmon Polaritons Ku-Band Satellite Receive Antenna," in 2024 11th International Symposium on Telecommunications (IST), 2024, pp. 135–140. doi: 10.1109/IST64061.2024.10843596.
- [13] D. J. Kern, D. H. Werner, and M. J. Wilhelm, "Active negative impedance loaded EBG structures for the realization of ultra-wideband artificial magnetic conductors," *IEEE Antennas Propag. Soc. AP-S Int. Symp.*, vol. 2, pp. 427–430, 2003, doi: 10.1109/aps.2003.1219267.
- [14] R. B. Hwang and Y. L. Tsai, "Reflection characteristics of a composite planar AMC surface," *AIP Adv.*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2012, doi: 10.1063/1.3682352.
- [15] P. Prakash, M. P. Abegaonkar, A. Basu, and S. K. Koul, "Gain enhancement of a CPW-Fed monopole antenna using polarization-insensitive AMC structure," *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.*, vol. 12, pp. 1315–1318, 2013, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2013.2285121.
- [16] Y. Zhang, J. Von Hagen, M. Younis, C. Fischer, and W. Wiesbeck, "Planar Artificial Magnetic Conductors and Patch Antennas," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 51, no. 10, pp. 2704–2712, 2003, doi: 10.1109/TAP.2003.817550.
- [17] R. Shinozaki, J. Tamura, and H. Arai, "Thin AMC substrate by applying square patch with semicircle notch," vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 704–708, 2021, doi: 10.1002/mop.29943.
- [18] R. Dewan et al., "Artificial magnetic conductor for various antenna applications: An overview," *Int. J. RF Microw. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 1–18, 2017, doi: 10.1002/mmce.21105.
- [19] A. Foroozesh and L. Shafai, "Effects of artificial magnetic conductors in the design of low-profile high-gain planar antennas with high-permittivity dielectric superstrate," *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.*, vol. 8, pp. 10–13, 2009, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2008.916684.
- [20] F. Costa, S. Genovesi, and A. Monorchio, "On the bandwidth of high-impedance frequency selective surfaces," *IEEE Antennas Wirel. Propag. Lett.*, vol. 8, pp. 1341–1344, 2009, doi: 10.1109/LAWP.2009.2038346.